

Article

The Role of Saltmarsh Restoration in Lowering Shoreline Vulnerability Within an Urban Estuary Environment: A Case Study from North of Portugal

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Abstract

Sea-level rise is accelerating coastal erosion and storm-driven flooding, increasing risks to estuarine ecosystems and coastal communities. Nature-based solutions (NbS), such as those including ecosystem restoration, are widely endorsed for climate change risk mitigation, yet their protective performance under rising sea levels remains poorly quantified across future scenarios. Here we combined scenario-based modelling with spatially explicit exposure mapping to assess how saltmarshes influence shoreline vulnerability under three Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) sea-level rise projections for 2050 and 2100. Using the InVEST Coastal Vulnerability Model and the Lima estuary (NW Portugal) as a case study, we showed that existing saltmarshes currently reduce mean shoreline exposure by approximately 5%, but this contribution declines with sea-level rise, falling to 2.6% by 2100 under SSP5-8.5, resulting in an increase in areas subject to High and Very High exposure risk. But under a saltmarsh revegetation scenario, model results indicated that this revegetation significantly increases the protection across all future scenarios, reducing the number of shoreline points in High and Very High exposure classes by up to 58% and lowering the potential coastal population exposure by up to 27% by 2100 under SSP5-8.5. However, the protective effect of saltmarshes diminished under the most extreme sea-level rise trajectories, indicating that saltmarsh revegetation alone may not be enough to fully offset accelerating coastal hazards. Our results demonstrate that saltmarsh restoration can deliver meaningful climate adaptation benefits; however, to safeguard estuarine systems and coastal communities under accelerating climate change in the long term, restoration actions must be integrated into broader adaptation strategies.

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1. Introduction

Coastal flooding and erosion are intensifying globally, increasing the pressure on ecosystems, communities and infrastructure [1,2]. Expanding coastal development and

other anthropogenic activities compound these pressures, making coastal systems among the most vulnerable on the planet [3–6]. Climate change is expected to exacerbate these trends through accelerating sea level rise (SLR) and increased storm frequency and intensity [7]. Coastal erosion results from the complex interaction of waves, currents, winds and storm surges, and is often amplified by infrastructures that could disrupt sediment dynamics [8]. Upstream dams and channel modifications may further reduce sediment supply, thereby accelerating downstream erosion [9]. Together, these pressures compromise the ecological integrity and socioeconomic value of coastal ecosystems, along with the Ecosystem Services (ES) and Societal Goods and Benefits (SGB) they provide [10]. These include carbon sequestration, habitat provision, and their role in mitigating storm and flood hazards [5,11–13] through wave energy attenuation or sediment retention [14–16].

Nature-based solutions (NbS) are increasingly recognized as effective strategies for climate adaptation and flood risk mitigation [17–20]. Restoring coastal habitats such as saltmarshes, seagrasses or dune systems can help regain the ES and societal benefits they supply [11,21,22], particularly those relevant for climate change mitigation [5,23–25]. In some contexts, NbS can offer benefits that outweigh their implementation/maintenance costs and equal or outperform hard infrastructure in long-term cost-effectiveness, when co-benefits such as increased biodiversity, recreation and other ES are considered [26,27]. However, NbS effectiveness is highly context-dependent and influenced not only by environmental features such as geomorphology, hydrodynamics and ecosystem condition, but also by socio-economic drivers [28]. Scenario-based assessments are essential as managers and policy-makers require evidence that explicitly links ecological restoration to future climate risk reduction. To implement measures that enhance the resistance and resilience of coastal communities against such pressures, science should provide spatially explicit and scenario-driven tools capable of informing adaptive decision-making.

SLR and storm-induced erosion and flooding mitigation benefits are often assessed through economic cost–benefit analysis [29]. However, relatively few studies quantify how coastal habitats reduce vulnerability under multiple climate trajectories (e.g., [11,30–32]) and particularly within ecosystem restoration contexts [33,34].

In this study, we integrate projected saltmarsh decline under the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) SLR scenarios with a revegetation simulation within a coastal vulnerability framework to investigate the potential of saltmarsh restoration through revegetation to reduce shoreline vulnerability. The Lima estuary, an urban estuarine system of NW Portugal, was used as a case study. In addition, we also assessed potential population exposure against SLR and storm-induced erosion and flooding.

The vulnerability of the estuarine shoreline was assessed under current and future SLR scenarios, both with and without the implementation of saltmarsh revegetation. The specific objectives were to: (1) assess current and projected future changes in shoreline vulnerability under three IPCC SLR scenarios along the estuary; (2) evaluate the effectiveness of simulated revegetation in reducing overall shoreline vulnerability; and (3) quantify the associated SGB, expressed as changes in the number of potentially affected people across scenarios. By linking shoreline vulnerability with potential population exposure, this study provides decision-relevant evidence, supporting the application of effective saltmarsh restoration initiatives under accelerating SLR.

2. Methods

2.1. Methodological Approach

The contribution and effectiveness of a saltmarsh restoration through revegetation in mitigating SLR-driven erosion and inundation were evaluated using a two-step approach. First, shoreline vulnerability was assessed under *Current* and future scenarios using the

Exposure Index (EI) from the Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Trade-offs (InVEST®) Coastal Vulnerability Model. Future scenarios considered were three IPCC Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) SLR projections and the respective projected salt-marsh area loss. The contribution of saltmarshes to protection was quantified through the difference in vulnerability with and without saltmarshes. Second, a *Revegetation* scenario was implemented by simulating new saltmarsh belts along consistently high-exposure shoreline sections. Shoreline vulnerability was modelled under identical SLR projections to quantify the additional protective effect. Potential societal benefits were also estimated by calculating the number of potentially affected people associated with shoreline points classified as High or Very High EI for each scenario.

2.2. Study Area

The Lima estuary (NW Portugal) is a temperate estuary approximately 20 km long, located near the city of Viana do Castelo and characterized by a semidiurnal, mesotidal regime regulated by two upstream hydroelectric dams (Figure 1). The estuary has high ecological relevance (e.g., [35,36]), providing key nursery habitats for diverse fish species and supporting bird migration routes. Its lower section is characterized by artificial embankments, a deep and narrow channel, and an international commercial port. The middle estuary comprises broad, shallow zones with tidal islands and saltmarshes, designated under the EU Natura 2000 network, while the upper estuary narrows into a shallow channel [37].

Figure 1. Case study area in the Lima estuary, showing the estuarine saltmarsh (in green) and the location of the model shore points (black dots) along the estuarine margins.

Saltmarshes are mostly located in the middle estuary and cover approximately 242 hectares distributed along the northern and southern margins. These habitats include well-developed low and upper saltmarsh communities dominated by species such

as *Juncus maritimus* Lam., *Phragmites australis* (Cav.) Trin. ex Steud., or *Sporobolus pumilus* (Roth) P.M. Peterson & Saarela. The estuary also contains several tidal islands largely covered by *J. maritimus* and *S. pumilus*. These saltmarshes provide essential ES, including carbon sequestration and storage [38] and contaminant removal/retention [38–40]. However, they are vulnerable to both anthropogenic and climate-induced pressures, which have already led to substantial habitat degradation and loss [5,41,42]. In addition, projections indicate that saltmarsh losses due to SLR may range from 14% to 17% by 2050 under the least severe scenario (SSP1-1.9) to 19% to 87% by 2100 under the most severe scenario (SSP5-8.5) [38].

2.3. Coastal Vulnerability Model

The Coastal Vulnerability Model from InVEST[®] [43] is a widely recognized ES tool that has been successfully applied in numerous studies (e.g., [11,44,45]). The model produces a qualitative Exposure Index (EI) for coastal points, representing their relative exposure to erosion and storm-induced inundation derived from extreme weather events, based on multiple input variables, and allowing the assessment of the protection by natural habitats [43]. These include biophysical factors, habitat presence, and environmental stressors and are used as proxies for various complex shoreline processes that influence exposure to erosion and inundation. The model is intended as a relative exposure assessment tool rather than a deterministic hydrodynamic or inundation model, enabling consistent comparison of shoreline vulnerability across alternative habitat distributions, coastal geomorphological change, and climate scenarios. In this study, EI is used as an operational measure of relative shoreline exposure to erosion and storm-driven inundation within the case study area (hereafter referred to as shoreline vulnerability for brevity).

The model integrates various data sources to calculate the EI, including coastal geomorphology, elevation, habitat distribution, wind and wave conditions, storm surge potential, and SLR projections. Each input is qualitatively ranked on a scale from very low exposure (rank = 1) to very high exposure (rank = 5). The EI is determined as the geometric mean of the ranked inputs at each point, using the formula (Equation (1)):

$$EI = \left(R_{\text{Geomorphology}} R_{\text{Relief}} R_{\text{Habitats}} R_{\text{WindExposure}} R_{\text{WaveExposure}} R_{\text{Surge}} R_{\text{SLR}} \right)^{1/7} \quad (1)$$

For a complete description of the model, please see [43].

In this study, the model was applied across 593 points spaced at 100 m, distributed along the two Lima estuarine margins (Figure 1). Exposure levels across scenarios were classified into five categories: Very Low (<1), Low (<2), Moderate (<3), High (<4), and Very High (≥ 4).

2.4. Input Variables

Shoreline geomorphology vulnerability classification across the estuarine margins followed the methodology of [46,47]. Five geomorphic classes were identified along the estuary and ranked on a scale from 1 (very low vulnerability) to 5 (very high vulnerability): seawalls (1), small seawalls (2), bulkheads (2), riprap walls (3), bluffs (4), and sand beaches (5).

Relief data were obtained from the EU Digital Elevation Model (EU-DEM; available at eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/eu-dem), while bathymetric data were sourced from the European Marine Observation and Data Network [48]. Relief information is ranked by its percentile values by the Coastal Vulnerability model. Specifically, relief values between 81 and 100 percentile (Rank 1), between 61 and 80 percentile (Rank 2), between 41 and 60 percentile (Rank 3), between 21 and 40 percentile (Rank 4) and between 0 and 20 percentile (Rank 5). Current saltmarsh distribution was derived from the Portuguese

land cover map (available at snig.dgterritorio.gov.pt), while future saltmarsh extents were extracted from [38], which modelled saltmarsh loss under future SLR scenarios. In this case study, to test the saltmarsh capacity, we have included only natural habitat information for saltmarshes. For saltmarshes, the natural habitat ranking was set to 2, following the model documentation [43]. The protective distance of saltmarshes (the distance over which they reduce inland exposure) was determined through multiple measurements across the study area and set to 250 m.

Wind and wave data from the WAVEWATCH III model [49] and continental shelf boundaries were based on the default datasets included in the InVEST model. Similar to the ranking of the Relief variable, the Coastal Vulnerability also ranks wave exposure and surge potential according to their percentile values namely, values between 81 and 100 percentile (Rank 1), between 61 and 80 percentile (Rank 2), between 41 and 60 (Rank 3), between 21 and 40 percentile (Rank 4) and between 0 and 20 percentile (Rank 5).

2.5. Scenarios and Simulations

Potential changes in the EI were modelled under the current conditions, multiple future SLR scenarios, and in a *Revegetation* scenario. For the *Current scenario*, EI was modelled using the current saltmarsh extent to assess and quantify its protective service. For *Future scenarios*, EI was modelled using SLR projections corresponding to the 5th, 50th, and 95th percentiles under three SSPs (SSP1-2.6, SSP2-4.5, and SSP5-8.5), based on the latest IPCC projections [50]. These scenarios were chosen to represent a range of potential SLR trajectories, i.e., different levels of SLR from low to high SLR projections. Saltmarsh loss for each scenario and percentile projection was based on the best corresponding values of low, intermediate and high habitat loss projections from [38]. Local SLR estimates were obtained for the Leixões Port area (Matosinhos) from the NASA sea level database (Table S1). Sea level change was ranked based on the percentile, similar to the other model variables described above.

To evaluate the potential reduction in EI across scenarios, each scenario was additionally modelled with a *Revegetation* simulation. This consisted of simulating a 30 m wide saltmarsh revegetated belt [51], along two sections of the Lima estuarine margins that were consistently identified as highly vulnerable across scenarios (Figure S1). The selection of these areas was based on EI results and balanced by the suitability of the areas to be revegetated in terms of not coinciding with man-made areas. However, no explicit prioritization of areas that would maximize the protection of human populations or infrastructure was done. This revegetation configuration was designed as an exploratory scenario rather than through formal spatial optimization.

To isolate the effects of saltmarshes' presence on vulnerability reduction, each scenario was modelled both with and without saltmarshes. In total, 38 simulations were conducted (Table S2), integrating three SLR projections percentiles under three climate scenarios, the two saltmarsh area configurations, subject to sea-level rise-driven habitat loss: (i) current saltmarsh (existing saltmarsh area) and (ii) revegetation (existing saltmarsh area plus additional revegetation area). This approach allowed for assessing the potential range of future shoreline vulnerability to SLR and storm-induced erosion and flooding.

2.6. Societal Benefits Assessment

To quantify the societal benefits provided by saltmarshes in reducing erosion and storm-driven inundation, we estimated the population potentially affected within the study area under an extreme coastal event scenario. Population raster data for 2025 [52] were used in the model using a 50 m radius (half the shore-point spacing) to minimize overlap and reduce potential double-counting when aggregating across points. Population numbers were

held constant across all scenarios. Given the positive relationship between High or Very High EI classifications and potential impacts [11], only population counts linked to these EI categories were aggregated and reported for each scenario, reflecting spatial coincidence between high shoreline exposure and resident population. It is of note that this metric is used only as a way to indicate potential societal benefits changes from the application of revegetation initiatives and represents current settlement exposure, rather than realized flood risk. This quantification does not include future demographic projections, and it does not account for adaptive capacity, behavioural responses, flood depth or duration, and thus, should be viewed as a simplified indicator of relative population exposure.

2.7. Scenario Comparison and Data Analysis

For each scenario, both the absolute and relative percentage changes in the mean EI were calculated. Absolute changes in EI resulting from the presence of saltmarshes were obtained by subtracting the mean EI of the scenario with saltmarshes from the mean EI of the corresponding scenario without saltmarshes (Equation (2)). Relative percentage changes between scenarios were calculated as:

$$((EI_{\text{Scenario}} - EI_{\text{Reference}})/EI_{\text{Reference}}) \times 100 \quad (2)$$

The same formulation was applied when comparing simulations within a given scenario, such as between simulations with current saltmarshes and those including saltmarsh revegetation. Class-wise changes were assessed by summing the number of shoreline points in each EI class for each scenario and computing absolute and relative changes using the same approach.

To test for statistically significant differences between the EI values of the *Current* scenario and the *Revegetation* scenario, a paired Wilcoxon signed-rank test was conducted. Effect sizes were quantified using rank-biserial correlation to assess the magnitude of differences between scenarios and simulations. Projected changes in the EI under future climate scenarios were performed by fitting a Generalized Linear Mixed Model (GLMM) with a Gamma distribution and log link, appropriate for positive continuous variables, with right-skewed distributions and repeated observations across shoreline points. Fixed effects included simulation type (revegetation vs. no revegetation), year, scenario, and percentile, while a random intercept for shoreline points was included to account for repeated observations at the same spatial locations across scenarios. Models were fitted using the `glmer` function in the `lme4` package [53] with the Nelder-Mead optimizer, using R [54]. Model residuals and convergence diagnostics were examined to verify fit adequacy. Estimated marginal means and pairwise contrasts between simulations were computed using the `emmeans` package [55]. Predicted means were back-transformed from the log scale to obtain response-scale ratios between the simulations with saltmarshes and revegetation for each combination of year and scenario, with 95% confidence intervals.

3. Results

3.1. Current Scenario

Under the *Current scenario*, the Lima estuary exhibited a mean EI of 2.46 ± 0.56 . Most shoreline points were classified as Moderate EI (51.6%), followed by Low (29.5%) and High (18.9%) EI (Figure 2A; Tables S3 and S4). Higher EI values were concentrated in the upstream sector and along the southern margin, with additional clusters near major saltmarsh areas in the middle estuary. Comparison with simulations excluding saltmarshes (Figure 2B) demonstrated that existing saltmarshes reduce mean shoreline exposure by

4.71%, lowering EI from 2.58 ± 0.57 (EI without saltmarshes) to 2.46 ± 0.56 (EI with saltmarshes) (Table 1).

Figure 2. Spatial distribution of the Exposure Index class in the Lima estuary under the *Current scenario* with saltmarshes (A) and without saltmarshes (B).

Table 1. Mean shoreline protection (%) under each Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) climate scenario and saltmarsh configuration (Current and Revegetation). Protection values were calculated by comparing each scenario with its corresponding simulation without saltmarsh presence.

Year	Scenario	Protection (%)	Protection with Revegetation (%)
Current	Current	4.71	6.53
2050	SSP1-2.6	3.73	5.99
2050	SSP2-4.5	3.61	5.91
2050	SSP5-8.5	3.53	5.80
2100	SSP1-2.6	3.40	5.60
2100	SSP2-4.5	2.88	5.22
2100	SSP5-8.5	2.65	5.05

3.2. Future Climate Change Scenarios

3.2.1. Mid-Term Scenarios (2050)

Under 2050 SLR scenarios, shoreline vulnerability increased progressively with SLR severity across all SSPs (Figures 3, S2 and S3, Tables 1, S3 and S4). Mean EI ranged from 2.56 ± 0.59 (SLR projections corresponding to the 5th percentiles) to 2.83 ± 0.65 (SLR projections corresponding to the 95th percentiles) under SSP1-2.6, 2.58 ± 0.59 to 2.84 ± 0.65 under SSP2-4.5, and 2.61 ± 0.60 to 2.85 ± 0.66 under SSP5-8.5. Consequently, the protective contribution of saltmarshes declined to 3.73% (SSP1-2.6), 3.61% (SSP2-4.5), and 3.53% (SSP5-8.5) (Table 1).

Figure 3. Spatial distribution of the Exposure Index (EI) class in the Lima estuary for the different scenarios, considering the current saltmarsh extent, under the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) climate and habitat loss scenarios for 2050 (**above**) and 2100 (**below**).

Overall, there was an increase in the shoreline vulnerability under all future scenarios. For example, under SSP1-2.6, there was an increase in the High EI points, representing 32–51% of the shoreline segments, while there was a decrease in the EI Moderate points (33–41%). Similar patterns were observed under SSP2-4.5 (Low: 15–24%; Moderate: 33–43%; High: 32–52%) and SSP5-8.5 (Low: 13–23%; Moderate: 34–43%; High: 34–51%; Very High: 0–0.5%).

3.2.2. Long-Term Scenarios (2100)

Under the 2100 SLR scenarios, there was a tendency for an overall increase in the mean EI. Mean EI increased to 2.68 ± 0.62 – 3.07 ± 0.70 under SSP1-2.6, 2.75 ± 0.63 – 3.16 ± 0.72 under SSP2-4.5, and 2.88 ± 0.66 – 3.28 ± 0.76 under SSP5-8.5 (Figures 3, S2 and S3, Tables 1, S3 and S4). Consequently, the saltmarsh protection declined, reaching 3.4% under SSP1-2.6, 2.9% under SSP2-4.5, and 2.6% under SSP5-8.5 (Table 1).

The distribution of EI classes showed pronounced shifts toward higher vulnerability in the Lima estuary. Under SSP1-2.6, Low EI accounted for 9–20% of shoreline points, Moderate for 29–39%, High for 40–56%, and Very High for 0.5–5%. Under SSP2-4.5, Low EI points declined to 9–15%, and Moderate ranged from 28 to 39%, whereas High exposure points increased to 45–55%, and Very High to 0.5–7.0%. The most severe scenario (SSP5-8.5) exhibited the strongest shift, with Low EI decreasing to 6–12%, Moderate to 29–35%, High increasing to 46–58%, and Very High reaching up to 18% of shoreline segments (Table S4).

3.3. Revegetation Scenarios

3.3.1. Current Scenario

The *Revegetation* scenario significantly reduced shoreline exposure relative to the *Current* scenario (Figure 4). Mean EI declined from 2.46 ± 0.56 to 2.42 ± 0.53 , corresponding to a significant 1.8% reduction (Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $p < 0.001$; moderate effect size, $r = 0.39$). Estuarine areas with High EI decreased by 41%, while areas with Moderate EI increased by 15%, reflecting a shift toward lower vulnerability classes (Table S4).

Figure 4. Spatial distribution of the Exposure Index class in the Lima estuary under the *Current* scenario with saltmarshes (A) and in the *Revegetation* scenario (B). Panel (C) shows the proportion of shoreline points within each Exposure Index class for the two scenarios.

3.3.2. Mid-Term Scenarios (2050)

Under 2050 SLR scenarios, the saltmarsh revegetation consistently reduced shoreline mean EI across all SSPs considered (Figures 5 and 6; Table 1). Mean EI ranged from 2.51 ± 0.55 to 2.77 ± 0.61 in SSP1-2.6, 2.53 ± 0.56 to 2.78 ± 0.62 in SSP2-4.5, and from 2.55 ± 0.57 to 2.79 ± 0.62 in SSP5-8.5. When assessing the protective service provided by revegetation, results showed that shoreline protection increased to 5.99%, 5.91%, and 5.8% for SSP1-2.6, SSP2-4.5, and SSP5-8.5, respectively.

Figure 5. Spatial distribution of the Exposure Index class in the Lima estuary for the revegetation scenarios under the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) climate and habitat loss scenarios for 2050 (above) and 2100 (below).

Figure 6. Distribution of shoreline points across Exposure Index classes in the Lima estuary for 2050 (A) and 2100 (B) under future Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) climate and habitat loss scenarios for the two saltmarsh extents under study (*Current* and *Revegetation*).

At the class level, areas with High EI declined by 8–27% under SSP1-2.6, 7.5–28.5% under SSP2-4.5, and 7–21% under SSP5-8.5. Very High exposure segments were reduced by up to 33% in SSP5-8.5 (Table S4).

3.3.3. Long-Term Scenarios (2100)

Under 2100 SLR scenarios, revegetation continued to reduce shoreline exposure (Figures 5 and 6; Tables 1, S3 and S4). Mean EI ranged from 2.62 ± 0.58 to 3.00 ± 0.67 under SSP1-2.6, 2.69 ± 0.59 to 3.07 ± 0.68 under SSP2-4.5, and 2.81 ± 0.62 to 3.18 ± 0.71 under SSP5-8.5. Overall, revegetation led to a shoreline protection increase to 5.6% in SSP1-2.6, to 5.22% in SSP2-4.5 and 5.05% in SSP5-8.5.

Areas with High EI decreased by 1–17% under SSP1-2.6, 1.5–10% under SSP2-4.5, and 5–16% under SSP5-8.5. Areas with Very High EI declined more markedly, by 33–58% across all SSP scenarios (Table S4). Despite reduced relative effectiveness under stronger SLR, *Revegetation* scenarios consistently exhibited significantly lower EI values compared to scenarios with saltmarshes ($p < 0.001$ across all scenarios).

Model results indicated that revegetation significantly reduced shoreline EI across all future scenarios considered ($\beta = -0.0208 \pm 0.0003$, $p < 0.001$). It also showed a slight decline in the protection benefits of the revegetation scenarios towards 2100, through the small but significant interaction between simulation and year ($\beta = -0.0018 \pm 0.0005$, $p = 0.0002$).

4. Societal Benefits

Under the *Current* scenario, model results indicate an estimated 669 people within the study area could potentially be exposed to an extreme coastal event (Figure 7, Table S5). This represents a substantial reduction of nearly 82% compared to the 3546 people estimated in the absence of saltmarshes. Implementation of the *Revegetation* scenario

further reduced this number by 9.6%, lowering the estimate to 605 people. Across future scenarios, the potentially affected population increased progressively under both mid and long-term SLR scenarios, with the magnitude of increase depending on the extent of projected saltmarsh loss.

Figure 7. Estimated population potentially affected under current and future Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) climate scenarios. The *Current* scenario compares conditions with the *Current saltmarsh extent* and *under the Revegetation scenario*. Future projections are presented for each SSP under two saltmarsh configurations: *Current saltmarsh* and *Revegetation extents* under projected sea level rise-driven habitat loss. Please note that bars represent median (50th percentile) sea-level rise projections, and error bars indicate the 5th and 95th percentile range.

Under 2050 SLR scenarios with saltmarshes present, the estimated number of potentially affected people ranged from 1061 to 6055 under SSP1-2.6, 1080 to 7993 under SSP2-4.5, and 1193 to 7993 under SSP5-8.5. *Revegetation* consistently reduced these estimates, with estimated numbers declining to 884–5789 (4–19% reduction) under SSP1-2.6, to 884–5817 (7–27% reduction) under SSP2-4.5, and to 1003–5817 (6–27% reduction) under SSP5-8.5.

Under 2100 SLR scenarios, the estimated potentially affected people increased substantially across all SSPs considered. With saltmarshes present, estimates ranged from 1605 to 10,348 under SSP1-2.6, 4895 to 10,405 under SSP2-4.5, and 7793 to 10,973 under SSP5-8.5. In comparison, the *Revegetation* scenario moderated these increases, reducing the estimates of affected people to 1252–8142 under SSP1-2.6 (4–22% reduction), 4689–10,119 under SSP2-4.5 (2–25% reduction), and 5817–10,844 under SSP5-8.5 (1–27% reduction).

5. Discussion

This study provides a spatially explicit assessment of how estuarine saltmarsh persistence and restoration may influence estuarine shoreline vulnerability under future SLR in the Lima estuary. By integrating climate-driven saltmarsh loss projections, multiple SLR trajectories, and a restoration scenario within a common vulnerability framework, we demonstrate that saltmarshes currently provide measurable protection against shoreline exposure in the Lima estuary. However, this protective function is likely to decline

as habitat extent decreases under future climate change. Our results show that targeted revegetation can partially offset these projected losses, reducing both shoreline exposure and potential population exposure across a wide range of future scenarios. Together, these findings highlight both the potential and the limitations of restoration-based adaptation in highly constrained urban estuaries.

5.1. Current Protection by Lima Estuarine Saltmarshes

Our findings show that saltmarshes currently contribute to reducing shoreline exposure to storm-induced erosion and inundation in the Lima estuary. The presence of existing saltmarshes reduced mean shoreline exposure relative to scenarios without habitat protection, supporting extensive empirical evidence that saltmarsh vegetation attenuates wave energy, dampens storm surges, and promotes sediment stabilization [12,56,57]. The spatial distribution of exposure further indicated that the highest vulnerability was concentrated in upstream sectors and along the southern estuarine margin, where geomorphological conditions and limited intertidal habitat reduce the capacity of natural systems to buffer hydrodynamic forcing.

Although the reduction in mean EI under Current conditions was modest, this result is consistent with the geomorphological context of the Lima estuary [58]. Unlike extensive coastal marsh systems where large wetland complexes can provide substantial attenuation distances, the Lima estuary is characterized by constrained intertidal areas, walled shorelines, and limited opportunities for habitat expansion. Consequently, the protective contribution of saltmarshes is inherently context-dependent and reflects the interaction between habitat extent, geomorphology, and hydrodynamic exposure of the Lima estuary. Similar spatial variability in ES delivery has been reported in other estuarine and coastal systems, where local geomorphological constraints strongly influence the magnitude of nature-based protection benefits [11,58,59].

5.2. Future Vulnerability Under Climate Change

Across all climate scenarios, shoreline vulnerability intensified through the 21st century, with increases in mean EI and in High or Very High EI areas, with the largest increases occurring under higher-emission pathways and towards 2100. Simultaneously, the capacity of existing saltmarsh to reduce exposure declined, reflecting projected losses in saltmarsh extent under climate-driven SLR. These trends reflect the combined effects of SLR and projected reductions in saltmarsh extent, resulting in a progressive loss of natural coastal protection.

The projected decline in protective capacity is consistent with the pervasive effects of “coastal squeeze” [60], whereby saltmarshes are unable to migrate landward due to topographic and anthropogenic barriers. This mechanism is particularly relevant in the Lima estuary and other Portuguese estuarine saltmarshes where substantial portions of the shoreline are constrained by infrastructure, embankments, and adjacent land uses [38].

The increasing prevalence of High and Very High exposure classes under future scenarios highlights the potential for nonlinear increases in estuarine vulnerability as habitat area declines. More importantly, the reduction in protection observed in this study is not solely a consequence of rising water levels but also of the loss of the natural infrastructure that currently contributes to shoreline stabilization and protection. This distinction is relevant for coastal adaptation planning because it emphasizes that climate impacts may arise both directly through physical forcing and indirectly through degradation of protective habitats [61].

Consequently, future habitat losses may trigger not only ecological degradation but also a reduction in the regulating ES and other functions provided by saltmarshes, including

shoreline stabilization and attenuation of storm impacts [38,62]. The increasing exposure identified in this study therefore highlights the growing challenge of maintaining estuarine resilience under accelerating SLR and reinforces the importance of proactive adaptation strategies that preserve or expand intertidal habitat extent [62]. Additionally, the divergence between current and future exposure conditions highlights that assessments based solely on current habitat distributions may substantially underestimate future vulnerability. By explicitly incorporating projected habitat loss into vulnerability assessments, this study demonstrates that the effectiveness of nature-based protection cannot be assumed to remain constant through time and must instead be evaluated within a dynamic climate-change context [32,62].

5.3. Restoration Potential and Implications for Adaptation Planning

The simulated *Revegetation* scenarios consistently reduced shoreline EI relative to scenarios containing only projected future saltmarsh distributions. Across climate pathways, revegetation lowered mean EI values, reduced the proportion of highly exposed shoreline segments, and decreased the number of potentially exposed residents. These findings indicate that strategically expanding saltmarsh extent can partially compensate for climate-driven habitat losses and contribute to maintaining coastal protection services under future conditions.

The effectiveness of revegetation was particularly evident in mid-term (2050) scenarios, where revegetation offset a substantial portion of the projected increases in EI. However, the relative benefit of revegetation declined slightly toward 2100, as indicated by both the scenario comparisons and the mixed-model results. This pattern could potentially suggest that restoration can enhance resilience but could potentially not entirely counteract the cumulative effects of accelerating SLR and habitat loss, particularly under higher-emission pathways. These findings are consistent with global assessments, which emphasize that ecosystem restoration can reduce climate risks while simultaneously supporting biodiversity and the provision of other ES [28,63–65]. However, they also reinforce growing recognition that ecosystem-based adaptation could potentially have limits, depending on the severity of projections of SLR. As sea levels continue to rise, restoration benefits may diminish where saltmarsh accretion cannot keep pace with inundation, where migration space is unavailable, or where geomorphological constraints restrict habitat development [66,67].

Consequently, revegetation should not be viewed as a potential standalone adaptation measure. Instead, it is likely to be most effective when integrated within broader adaptation portfolios that combine ecological restoration, engineered protection, land-use planning, and, where necessary, managed retreat [8,64,67]. Such hybrid approaches may be particularly important in urban estuaries, where high levels of infrastructure and land-use intensity constrain the capacity of natural habitats to migrate and persist [68].

An important finding is that revegetation reduced potential population exposure even though restoration sites were selected based on shoreline vulnerability rather than explicitly targeting populated environments. This highlights the broader societal benefits that can arise from ecosystem restoration and strengthens the case for incorporating saltmarsh restoration within climate adaptation and nature-based solution frameworks [69]. The revegetation performance in lowering the EI in the Lima estuary varied among climate scenarios, indicating that adaptation benefits cannot be adequately assessed under static environmental conditions. In a broader context, the long-term robustness and success of these types of initiatives are contingent upon their integration in accordance with the standards and principles of NbS [63]. It is crucial that such initiatives are designed with consideration of the varying scales of the processes involved. In addition to the consideration of ecological and physical processes, it is imperative that these solutions

encompass the multifaceted landscape of climatic, economic and socio-cultural perspectives. Moreover, studies such as the present one, which evaluate the effectiveness of revegetation across a range of climate scenarios as opposed to under static conditions, are of paramount importance to stakeholders and policymakers when determining the potential for the success of such initiatives in the future. This gains particular importance in urban estuaries, where ecological opportunities are often constrained by competing land uses and limited space for habitat migration. Ultimately, the results of this study provide spatially explicit evidence supporting the integration of saltmarsh restoration into long-term adaptation planning and the transformative change that needs to occur in society for the necessary climate adaptation [70–72].

Overall, this study demonstrates that saltmarsh restoration can meaningfully enhance estuarine resilience, but could potentially not fully counterbalance accelerating SLR under high-emission scenarios. By explicitly quantifying both the benefits and limits of restoration across climate trajectories, this study contributes to a more realistic understanding of revegetation performance under climate change. Safeguarding estuarine systems will require adaptive, multidisciplinary strategies that combine preserving the ecological assets and promoting social benefits. Scaling the application of revegetation initiatives must therefore proceed alongside recognition of their ecological thresholds, ensuring that solutions are deployed strategically within broader adaptation pathways, considering a landscape-level approach and integrated into NbS, designed to anticipate increasing SLR.

5.4. Limitations and Uncertainty

While the InVEST Coastal Vulnerability Model allowed a comprehensive integration of biophysical and socio-economic data into a simple framework to assess the relative exposure of shorelines, several limitations should be considered when interpreting the findings of this study. First, the InVEST Coastal Vulnerability model provides a relative exposure index rather than physically explicit predictions of flood depth, erosion rates, or inundation extent (Natural Capital Project, 2025). Consequently, the results should be interpreted as comparative assessments of relative shoreline exposure among scenarios rather than deterministic estimates of future impacts. The strength of the approach lies in its ability to consistently compare alternative scenarios using readily available environmental information. Second, habitat protection is represented as a static and spatially uniform reduction in exposure. In reality, saltmarsh attenuation capacity is highly nonlinear and depends on factors such as marsh width, vegetation structure, edge condition or sediment availability [57]. Hence, considering that wider, more developed saltmarshes may provide disproportionately greater protection, and in contrast, degraded or fragmented saltmarshes may provide lower protection, the projected local protection benefits may be under or over-estimated in some shoreline sectors. Third, although multiple SSPs, percentile-based SLR projections, and projected saltmarsh distributions were incorporated, uncertainty associated with local SLR downscaling and habitat-response dynamics was not explicitly partitioned. The scenario ranges presented here should therefore be interpreted as plausible future conditions rather than fully probabilistic uncertainty envelopes. Fourth, the revegetation scenarios assumed successful establishment, persistence, and full functional equivalence of restored marshes, as stated above. As restored saltmarshes may require years to develop mature vegetation structure and sediment-trapping capacity [57,73], the estimated benefits likely represent optimistic long-term outcomes, rather than immediate restoration gains. If the establishment of revegetation areas fails, it is hypothesized that EI values for the specific shoreline segments would potentially revert to the modelled scenario without revegetation or, assuming partial functionality, EI would be constrained to values in between those two modelled scenarios. Furthermore, the *Revegetation* configuration was designed as an

exploratory scenario rather than a formal optimization exercise, and alternative restoration layouts, marsh widths, and spatial configurations were not evaluated.

Fifth, the population exposure estimates were based on current population distributions and did not account for future changes in demographics or adaptation measures that could lead to modifications in the societal consequences. Consequently, they should be interpreted as indicators of relative societal exposure rather than projections of future impacts. Finally, the analysis was conducted at a single shoreline resolution (100 m spacing). Although sufficient to capture the principal geomorphological and habitat characteristics of the Lima estuary, vulnerability patterns may vary across spatial scales [74,75]. Future work could evaluate the robustness of the results using alternative shoreline resolutions, determining the extent to which restoration priorities and vulnerability patterns remain consistent across scales. In addition, although shoreline point identity was included as a random effect, residual spatial autocorrelation among neighbouring shoreline segments may still be present and could influence uncertainty estimates.

Future research could address these limitations through multi-scale analysis, integrating dynamic marsh models with hydrodynamic model simulations that could better capture geomorphological feedbacks and potential tipping points in estuarine resilience. The further integration of these models with decision-support tools would facilitate the collaborative design of adaptation strategies with local stakeholders, thereby ensuring that ecological, social, and economic dimensions are addressed collectively.

6. Conclusions

SLR is increasing the risk to estuarine systems worldwide. This spatially explicit assessment of the Lima estuary shows that shoreline vulnerability to erosion and storm-induced inundation will intensify substantially throughout the 21st century, particularly under high-emissions scenarios, as climate-driven exposure increases and saltmarsh extent potentially declines. Although existing saltmarshes provide natural protection to some degree, their buffering capacity in reducing relative shoreline exposure and their contribution to lowering future erosion and storm-driven inundation are projected to diminish under future SLR scenarios, reflecting the progressive loss of this important ES. Our results indicate that targeted saltmarsh revegetation can partially offset this loss. Across climate scenarios, restoration reduced the extent of highly vulnerable shoreline segments and lowered the number of potentially affected people, demonstrating that ecological restoration can translate directly into meaningful societal benefits. However, under extreme SLR scenarios, saltmarsh restoration alone is insufficient to fully counterbalance accelerating climatic pressures.

These findings highlight that the long-term effectiveness of revegetation initiatives in supporting coastal populations in coping with SLR may be limited if implemented in isolation, without integration into a broader NbS framework. By linking vulnerability modelling with estimates of potential population exposure, this study provides decision-relevant, spatially explicit evidence that restoring saltmarshes enhances both ecological resilience and human safety in the face of current and projected climate-driven pressures.

Supplementary Materials: The following supporting information can be downloaded at: <https://www.mdpi.com/article/10.3390/su18126329/s1>, Table S1. Sea level rise values (meters) used to model saltmarsh area loss. Projections were derived from the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report and extracted from the NASA Sea Level projection Tool (<https://sealevel.nasa.gov>) for Leixões harbour in Northern Portugal. Table S2. Condition used for each one of the simulations of this work. Figure S1. Current distribution of the saltmarsh areas in the Lima estuary and the location of the revegetation simulation implemented in the study. Table S3. Mean exposure index (EI) for each scenario modelled in this study, including the current scenario and saltmarsh configuration, and

for each socio-economic pathway (SSP) sea-level rise percentile projection. The table also shows the relative percentage change in mean EI between scenarios. Table S4. Distribution of the different Exposure Index (EI) classes, Very Low (<1), Low (<2), Moderate (<3), High (<4), and Very High (≥ 4), for each of the scenarios modeled in this study and for each saltmarsh simulation. Sea-level rise percentile projection is also indicated. Figure S2. Spatial distribution of the Exposure Index class in the Lima estuary for the scenarios without saltmarshes, under the 2050 Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) climate scenarios. Figure S3. Spatial distribution of the Exposure Index class in the Lima estuary for the scenarios without saltmarshes, under the 2100 Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) climate scenarios. Table S5. Potential affected population (people numbers) for each scenario and saltmarsh simulation modelled, and the relative percentage change between the scenarios. Sea-level rise percentile projection is also indicated.

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